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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“POWER OF PERSEVERANCE”

In the beginning, the road seemed thorny,
Challenges arose, pain still accompanied me,
But in the heart, a dream blazed bright,
Even in hardship, never ceasing to take flight.

In each failure, a lesson I have learned,
From the tears, strength grew, I have returned,
Weariness and pain, I embraced and endured,
For ahead, success awaits, ready to be secured.

No trial can topple my stance,
No obstacle can extinguish my dream's expanse,
For in the heart, strength reigns, unyielding,
Hope is my guide, the goal within my holding.

And now, here I am, at the journey's peak,
The fruits of searching, I've found, humbled and meek,
But this is not the end, but just the start,
For the flight in the light, continues, never apart.